

pots were infested with two 1st-instar larvae/tiller and enclosed in mylar film cages. Surviving larvae were determined 17 d after infestation.

To study host preference, 15-cm-diam petri dishes were divided into 6 areas. Three leaf pieces of each variety tested and 3 control leaf cuts were placed in alternate areas and 24 1st-instar larvae were placed in the center. Larvae settling on each leaf piece were counted at 24 h. Five replications were made.

O. brachyantha were more resistant than the *O. sativa* cultivars; fewer eggs were laid on them and fewer larvae survived (Table 1). Fewer larvae also settled on the wild rice leaves (Table 2).

Wild rices belonging to the *O. brachyantha* group have narrow, short leaves; *O. sativa* varieties have long, and broad leaves. Correlation of plant

Table 2. Attraction of rice LF larvae to *Oryza brachyantha* and *O. sativa* cultivars.^a IRRI, 1986.

<i>Oryza</i> spp.	Accession no.	Feeding preference (no. larvae/arena) ^b	Difference ^c
<i>O. brachyantha</i>	101232	8	56 **
	TN1	64	
<i>O. brachyantha</i>	101233	15	32 **
	TN1	47	
<i>O. brachyantha</i>	101234	16	42 **
	TN1	58	
<i>O. sativa</i>	45493	32	21 *
	TN1	59	
Kamalbhog	49020	34	27 *
	TN1	61	
Choorapundy	49529	34	17 *
	TN1	51	
TKM6	237	39	19 *
	TN1	58	

^a Av of 5 replications. n = 24. ^b Reading taken at 24 h. ^c Level of significance: ** = 0.01, * = 0.05. TN1 is the susceptible check.

characters and LF infestation showed that cultivars with longer, broader leaves had more damage. These

cultivars' leaves may have made folding easier, providing larger feeding areas. □

Green leafhopper (GLH) resistance in wild rices

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We evaluated 24 wild rices for resistance to GLH *Nephotettix virescens* under greenhouse conditions by the standard seedbox screening. Pregerminated seeds were sown in 60- × 40- × 10-cm seedboxes with resistant check Ptb 33 and susceptible check TN1. Each accession had five replications.

Seedlings were infested with 5 2d-instar nymphs/seedling 7 d after sowing. Damage was rated when 90-100% of susceptible TN1 seedlings died.

Sixteen wild rices were resistant, four were moderately resistant, and four were susceptible to *N. virescens* (see table). □

Reaction of wild rices to *Nephotettix virescens* in seedbox screening, TNAU, Coimbatore, India, 1985-86.

Species	Origin	IRRI acc. no.	Damage rating ^a
<i>Oryza latifolia</i>	Panama	100966	1 a
<i>O. punctata</i>	Ghana	101409	1 a
<i>O. nivara</i>	India	101510	1 a
<i>O. australiensis</i>	Australia	103318	1 a
<i>O. nivara</i>	Sri Lanka	103419	1 a
<i>O. glaberrima</i>	Senegal	103438	1 a
<i>O. rufipogon</i>	Venezuela	103810	1 a
<i>O. sativalo/O. spontanea</i>	Bangladesh	103826	1 a
<i>O. nivara</i>	Bangladesh	103835	1 a
<i>O. rufipogon</i>	Bangladesh	103844	1 a
<i>O. perennis</i>	India	103846	1 a
<i>O. perennis</i>	India	103848	1 a
<i>O. glaberrima</i>	Senegal	103439	3 b
<i>O. glaberrima</i>	Senegal	103443	3 b
<i>O. sativalo/O. spontanea</i>	Bangladesh	103831	3 b
<i>O. perennis</i>	India	103845	3 b
<i>O. nivara</i>	Australia	101466	5 c
<i>O. glaberrima</i>	Senegal	103437	5 c
<i>O. glaberrima</i>	Senegal	103488	5 c
<i>O. rufipogon/O. nivara</i>	Burma	103796	5 c
<i>O. minuta</i>	Philippines	101132	7 d
<i>O. eichingeri</i>	Tanzania	101171	7 d
<i>O. nivara/O. sativa</i>	Sri Lanka	103791	7 d
<i>O. nivara</i>	Bangladesh	103836	9 e
Ptb 33 (resistant check)			1 a
TN1 (susceptible check)			9 e

^a Mean of 5 replications. Damage rating based on 0-9 scale. Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by Duncan's multiple range test.

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